

Design of the resistor-capacitor snubber network for a d. c. circuit containing an inductive load

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Abstract: In most of the power electronic circuits, it is necessary to minimize the effect of the excessive rate of increase of the voltage across the devices due to which they could be overstressed. This effect is usually minimized by adopting the protective elements and circuits like snubber circuits, nonlinear surge – compressors, crowbar circuit etc. In this paper, we discuss a matrix method for the determination of components of resistor-capacitor snubber network connected in shunt with a silicon – controlled rectifier (SCR), and designed for a d. c. circuit containing an inductive load so that we can avoid the unintended breakover in the circuit due to the excessive rate of increase of the voltage across the SCR, resulting in the maloperation and failure of the circuit.

Keywords: Excessive rate of the increase of the voltage; circuit; snubber network.

Introduction: Most of the power electronic devices which work at high voltage level belong to the family of thyristor such as silicon – controlled rectifier (SCR), triode for alternating current (TRIAC), diode alternating current (DIAC), gate turn-off (GTO) etc. have different techniques such as forward voltage triggering, gate triggering, triggering by rate of change of voltage etc. to turn-on the device. In the case of triggering by the time rate of change of the voltage across the SCR, the inner junction of the SCR behaves like a capacitance. A charging current through this junction capacitance due suddenly appeared voltage across it may turn-on the SCR. It is noted that even if the voltage across the SCR is small, it is the rate of change of the voltage that turns it on and if this rate of change of voltage across the SCR is greater than its $\frac{dV}{dt}$ rating, then it would start conducting without triggering pulse at the gate. For the satisfactory and reliable operation of the circuit containing an SCR, it must be protected against all the abnormal conditions like false triggering of the SCR due to the excessive rate of increase of voltage across it. This protection is provided by the snubber network containing a resistor (R_s) - capacitor (C_s) series combination shunted from the SCR. The role of resistor (R_s) is to reduce the current discharged through the SCR. To minimize the effect of the excessive rate of increase of the voltage across the SCR it is necessary to determine the components of the RC snubber network so that false triggering of SCR, which results in the maloperation and failure of the circuit can be avoided [1, 2].

Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors:

Considering a homogeneous system of equations $(D - \mu I) T = 0$ which always has a non – trivial solution, where D is a matrix of order $n \times n$ with d_{ij} as its elements, T is a column matrix, I is an identity matrix and μ is a scalar. Then the eigenvalues of the matrix D are defined as those values of μ for which the non – trivial solutions of the system of homogeneous equations exist and the eigenvectors of the matrix D are the corresponding non – trivial solution vectors (or column matrices) T [3, 4].

Methodology:

Governing differential equation:

Considering a series resistor (R_s) – capacitor (C_s) snubber network connected in parallel to an SCR. The resulting snubber circuit is connected to a d. c. circuit consisting of a series combination of a load resistance R_L and a source inductance L as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Snubber circuit used in d.c. circuit.

Figure 2: Equivalent circuit.

In actual practice, a d. c. voltage is switched across the SCR, and the rate of change of voltage across the SCR must be below the $\frac{dV}{dt}$ rating of the SCR, otherwise, it would start conducting without the gate trigger pulse. As the switch is opened at $t=0$, the capacitor (C_s) behaves like a short circuit and the SCR in the forward blocking state offers a very high resistance to the current i.e. acts as an

open switch [1, 2]. The equivalent circuit for this situation is shown in figure (2). The application of Kirchhoff's loop law to the loop (figure 2) as the switch is opened at the instant $t = 0$ provides

$$V_{R_s}(t) + V_L(t) + V_{R_l}(t) = V_{dc}$$

$$\text{Or } R_s I(t) + L \frac{dI(t)}{dt} + R_l I(t) = V_{dc} \dots (1)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \equiv \frac{d}{dt}$$

The differentiation of equation (1) with respect to time t gives a linear homogeneous differential equation of order 2 as written below:

$$R_s \frac{dI(t)}{dt} + L \frac{d^2 I(t)}{dt^2} + R_l \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = 0$$

$$\text{Or } L \frac{d^2 I(t)}{dt^2} + (R_s + R_l) \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = 0$$

$$\text{Or } \frac{d^2 I(t)}{dt^2} + \frac{R_s + R_l}{L} \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = 0 \dots (2)$$

Solution of the differential equation:

To solve equation (2), we first write the initial conditions as follows:

- (i) It is known that the current cannot change instantaneously through the inductor [6], therefore, as the switch is opened at the instant $t = 0$, then $I(0) = 0$.
- (ii) Since at $t = 0$, $I(0) = 0$, therefore, equation (1) provides $L \frac{dI(0)}{dt} = V_{dc}$ or $\frac{dI(0)}{dt} = \frac{V_{dc}}{L}$.

$$\text{Further, let } I(t) = I_1(t) \dots \dots (3)$$

$$\frac{dI_1(t)}{dt} = I_2(t) \dots \dots (4)$$

$$\text{And for convenience } \frac{R_s + R_l}{L} = k, \dots (5)$$

Then we can rewrite equation (2) as

$$\frac{d^2 I_2(t)}{dt^2} + k I_2(t) = 0$$

$$\text{Or } \frac{dI_2(t)}{dt} = -k I_2(t) \dots (6)$$

We can write the differential equations (4) and (6) in a single matrix form as

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} I_1(t) \\ I_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1(t) \\ I_2(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

The characteristic equation (or eigenvalue equation) of the matrix $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -k^2 \end{bmatrix}$ is given by

$$\begin{vmatrix} 0 - \mu & 1 \\ 0 & -k - \mu \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

On expanding the determinant, we get $\mu^2 + k \mu = 0$

Or $\mu = 0, -k$ which are the eigenvalues of the matrix $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -k^2 \end{bmatrix}$.

Now the eigenvector for the eigenvalue $\mu = 0$ is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 - 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -k - 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This results

$$t_2 = 0$$

$$\text{Or } \frac{t_1}{1} = \frac{t_2}{0}$$

$$\text{Or } \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Now the eigenvector for the eigenvalue $\mu = -k$ is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 + k & 1 \\ 0 & -k + k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

This results

$$k t_1 + t_2 = 0$$

$$\text{Or } \frac{t_1}{1} = \frac{t_2}{-k}$$

$$\text{Or } \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ -k \end{bmatrix}$$

We can write the matrix of Eigenvectors as $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -k \end{bmatrix}$.

Let $P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -k \end{bmatrix}$, then the inverse of P is given by

$$P^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{k} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{k} \end{bmatrix}$$

Now we have to find $P e^{\mu z} P^{-1}$.

$$P e^{\mu z} P^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^{0t} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-kt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{k} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{k} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & e^{-kt} \\ 0 & -ke^{-kt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{k} \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{k} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{k}(1 - e^{-kt}) \\ 0 & e^{-kt} \end{bmatrix}$$

On application of initial conditions: $I_1(0) = I(0) = 0$ and $I_2(0) = \mathcal{D}_t[I(0)] = \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}$, we can write

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_1(t) \\ I_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \frac{1}{k}(1 - e^{-kt}) \\ 0 & e^{-kt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}} \end{bmatrix}$$

Or

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_1(t) \\ I_2(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{V_{dc}}{k\mathcal{L}}(1 - e^{-kt}) \\ \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}e^{-kt} \end{bmatrix}$$

This results

$$I_1(t) = \frac{V_{dc}}{k\mathcal{L}}(1 - e^{-kt})$$

Or

$$I(t) = \frac{V_{dc}}{k\mathcal{L}}(1 - e^{-kt})$$

Put the value of k from equation (5), we get

$$I(t) = \frac{V_{dc}}{R_s + R} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{(R_s + R)}{\mathcal{L}}t} \right) \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

And

$$I_2(t) = \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}e^{-kt}$$

Or

$$\mathcal{D}_t[I(t)] = \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}e^{-kt}$$

Put the value of k from equation (5), we get

$$\mathcal{D}_t[I(t)] = \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}e^{-\frac{(R_s + R)}{\mathcal{L}}t} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

The value of $\mathcal{D}_t[I(t)]$ is maximum when $t = 0$ i.e.

$$\mathcal{D}_t[I(t)]_{max} = \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}$$

$$\text{Or } \mathcal{L} = \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{D}_t[I(t)]_{max}} \dots \dots (9)$$

The maximum time rate of change of voltage across the SCR is obtained by applying the ohm's law and is given by

$$\mathcal{D}_t[V(t)]_{max} = R_s \mathcal{D}_t[I(t)]_{max}$$

$$\text{Or } \mathcal{D}_t[V(t)]_{max} = R_s \frac{V_{dc}}{\mathcal{L}}$$

$$\text{Or } R_s = \frac{\mathcal{L}}{V} \mathcal{D}_t[V(t)]_{max} \dots \dots (10)$$

The values of parameters \mathcal{L} , R_l , R_s , and C_s are so selected that the circuit becomes critically damped and the capacitor charges in the minimum possible time. Therefore, the application of condition of critical damping ^[5, 6] provides

$$R_s + R_l = \left(\frac{4\mathcal{L}}{C_s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\text{Or } (R_s + R_l)^2 = \frac{4\mathcal{L}}{C_s}$$

$$\text{Or } C_s = \frac{4\mathcal{L}}{(R_s + R_l)^2} \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

It is clear from equations (10) and (11) that by using the permissible value of $\mathcal{D}_t[V(t)]$ to avoid any maloperation of the SCR, and from the given values of \mathcal{L} and R_l , we can find the values of snubber network components R_s and C_s .

Conclusions: In this paper, we have obtained the rate of increase of the voltage in the snubber network connected to a d. c. circuit, and obtained the values of snubber components R_s and C_s for designing a snubber network to avoid the unnecessary breakover in the circuit due to the excessive rate of increase of voltage across the SCR, resulting in the maloperation and failure of the circuit by matrix method. It should be noted that before turning-on of the SCR, if the capacitor C_s is charged to the supply voltage, then after

turning-on of the SCR, the capacitor will provide a step increase in current through it and if the value of R_s is small, then this increase in current through the will be large. Hence, it is concluded that the value of R_s is slightly greater than the value required to limit the rate of increase of voltage across the SCR, and the value of C_s is small so that the discharge through the SCR at the time of its turning on, does not harm it.

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